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**EGFR T790M RESISTANCE MUTATION IN NON-SMALL-CELL LUNG CANCER:
OUR EXPERIENCE IN LIQUID BIOPSY AND MOLECULAR TESTING**

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Introduction: Patients with non-small-cell lung cancer (NSCLC) and epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) activating mutations will inevitably become resistant to the first- or second-generation tyrosine kinase inhibitors (TKIs). Approximately 40-55% of resistant cases are due to the acquired EGFR T790M mutation. Circulating DNA found in blood (liquid biopsy) has been proposed as an alternative source of tumor DNA. The aim of this study was the determination of EGFR T790M mutation frequency in investigated population.

Methods: This study included 33 NSCLC patients with EGFR mutations who had experienced progressive disease to TKIs at the Institute for Pulmonary Diseases of Vojvodina and the Special Hospital for Lung Diseases “Dr Jovan Bulajić “. The EGFR mutations were detected by the cobas[®] EGFR Mutation Test v2.

Results: All tested patients were of Caucasian descent and had the adenocarcinoma subtype of advanced NSCLC. There were 19 (57.6%) female and 14 (42.4%) male patients, the median age was 64.4 (range 43-78 years). The median progression-free survival was 13.6 months (range 2-36 months). All of 33 patients underwent liquid biopsy and T790M mutation was detected in plasma samples of 11 patients. Among the 22 T790M liquid biopsy-negative patients, 7 patients underwent re-biopsy procedures. Of the 7 patients in the rebiopsy group, T790M mutation was identified in 4 samples. Overall, T790M mutation rate established by liquid biopsy and re-biopsy was 45.5% (15/33). T790M always coexisted with a primary EGFR mutation.

Conclusions: Liquid biopsy and tissue biopsy should have complementary roles in identifying T790M-positive patients suitable for the treatment with the third generation TKI.

Key words: Lung cancer, EGFR, T790M, liquid biopsy